

Single-Crossed Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 42

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Abstract

*Recently, the author constructed even order magic squares from orders 6 to 30 with different styles and models, for examples the order 20 is with 1616 magic squares, order 18 with 810 magic squares, etc. These can be seen at [31, 32, 33, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37]. The aim is to proceed for the further orders of magic squares. A systematic procedure to construct these magic squares is given. It is based on the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 etc. at **corners** and small blocks of **bordered magic rectangles** forming external borders. Then the internal borders are filled with previous known magic squares. Instead of numbers, The presentation is in figures is given for the magic squares of even orders from 22 to 40. It can be seen at [38, 39, 40, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51]. In this work we have considered **crossed bordered magic rectangles** for the magic squares of order 40. It is done with **single crossed bordered magic rectangles**. The **double crossed bordered magic rectangles** are done in another work. The work is with few examples. The pdf file of full work can be downloaded at author's site [2].*

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1 Introduction

The magic sums of order n of consecutive numbers from 1 to n^2 is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}, n \geq 3. \quad (1)$$

Recently, the author [31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37] constructed magic squares of even orders from 8 to 20 using **bordered magic rectangles**. This construction is based on two aspects:

- (i) Using **magic rectangles** or **bordered magic rectangles**.
- (ii) Using algebraic formula like $(a + b)^2, a \neq b$.

For the above magic squares no construction procedure is explained. The aim is to proceed further orders of magic squares. In this work, a systematic procedure to construct these magic squares is given. It is based on the magic squares and bordered magic rectangles (BMR) of orders 4, 6, 8 etc forming external borders. Then the internal borders are filled with previous known magic squares. For the orders multiples of 4, we can always write magic squares with equal sums blocks of magic squares of order 4. This procedure is very helpful for the orders of type **2p**, where **p** is a prime number, for examples, 14, 22, 26, 34, 38, etc. For the orders like 18, 30, etc., we can make good external blocks with order 4, and for orders like 16, 20, 28, 32, etc. we can make good external borders of order 6, and so on. There is no explanations for the orders 6, 8, 10 and 12. The real construction starts from the order 14.

The whole the work is done manually, without use of any programming language, except for the constructions of small blocks of **bordered magic rectangles**. This construction is based on the software due to H. While [1]. Later, these BRMs are readopted according to distribution of each magic square. The distribution of **magic squares** or **bordered magic rectangles** is based on **half-sequential** numbers. By **half-sequential** numbers we understand that the total numbers in each case are divided in two equal parts. The first part is one sequence and the second part is another sequence. Due to **half-sequential** numbers, it is not possible to construct all orders **bordered magic rectangles**. In Appendix 3, there are tables showing the existence of these **bordered magic rectangles** for **half-sequential**. For simplicity, we shall write **BMR** as **bordered magic rectangle**. This work is for order 40. The previous works can be seen at [38, 39, 40, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51]. In this work we have considered **crossed bordered magic rectangles** for the magic squares of order 42. It is done with **single crossed bordered magic rectangles**. The **double crossed bordered magic rectangles** are done in another work. The work is with few examples. The pdf file of full work can be downloaded at author's site [2].

Remark 1. *The **bordered magic squares** and **bordered magic rectangles** are with the property that if we remove external borders in each case, still we are left with **bordered magic squares** and **bordered magic rectangles** respectively with sequential number entries. The whole work is in figures instead of numbers. In the same magic square the **small equal figures** represents equal sums **magic squares** and/or equal sums **bordered magic rectangles**.*

2 Cross-Type Magic Squares of Order 42

This section brings magic squares of order 42 in some special way, where the main bordered magic rectangles are written in **cross form**. There are 1366 single-crossed magic squares of order 42. Below are only few examples. The complete list is given as pdf file in author's site [2]

3 Appendix

Below are tables giving the existence of **bordered magic rectangles** for **half-sequential** numbers.

Order of Magic Square	Bordered Magic Rectangles
6	4×6
8	6×8
10	$4 \times 10, 8 \times 10$
12	$6 \times 12, 10 \times 12$
14	$4 \times 14, 8 \times 14, 12 \times 14$
16	$6 \times 16, 10 \times 16, 14 \times 16$
18	$4 \times 18, 8 \times 18, 12 \times 18$
20	$6 \times 20, 10 \times 20, 14 \times 20, 18 \times 20$
22	$4 \times 22, 8 \times 22, 12 \times 22,$ $16 \times 22, 20 \times 22$
24	$6 \times 24, 10 \times 24, 14 \times 24,$ $18 \times 24, 22 \times 24$
26	$4 \times 26, 8 \times 26, 12 \times 26,$ $16 \times 26, 20 \times 26, 24 \times 26$
28	$6 \times 28, 10 \times 28, 14 \times 28,$ $18 \times 28, 22 \times 28, 26 \times 28$
30	$4 \times 30, 8 \times 30, 12 \times 30, 16 \times 30,$ $20 \times 30, 24 \times 30, 28 \times 30$
32	$6 \times 32, 10 \times 32, 14 \times 32, 18 \times 32,$ $22 \times 32, 26 \times 32, 30 \times 32$
34	$4 \times 34, 8 \times 34, 12 \times 34, 16 \times 34,$ $20 \times 34, 24 \times 34, 28 \times 34, 32 \times 34$

Order of Magic Square	Bordered Magic Rectangles
36	$6 \times 36, 10 \times 36, 14 \times 36, 18 \times 36,$ $22 \times 36, 26 \times 36, 30 \times 36, 34 \times 36$
38	$4 \times 38, 8 \times 38, 12 \times 38, 16 \times 38, 20 \times 38,$ $24 \times 38, 28 \times 38, 32 \times 38, 36 \times 38$
40	$6 \times 40, 10 \times 40, 14 \times 40, 18 \times 40, 22 \times 40,$ $26 \times 40, 30 \times 40, 34 \times 40, 38 \times 40$
42	$4 \times 42, 8 \times 42, 12 \times 42, 16 \times 42, 20 \times 42,$ $24 \times 42, 28 \times 42, 32 \times 42, 36 \times 42, 40 \times 42$
44	$6 \times 44, 10 \times 44, 14 \times 44, 18 \times 44, 22 \times 44, 26 \times 44,$ $30 \times 44, 34 \times 44, 38 \times 44, 42 \times 44$
46	$4 \times 46, 8 \times 46, 12 \times 46, 16 \times 46, 20 \times 46, 24 \times 46,$ $28 \times 46, 32 \times 46, 36 \times 46, 40 \times 46, 44 \times 46$
48	$6 \times 48, 10 \times 48, 14 \times 48, 18 \times 48, 22 \times 48, 26 \times 48,$ $30 \times 48, 34 \times 48, 38 \times 48, 42 \times 48, 46 \times 48$
50	$4 \times 50, 8 \times 50, 12 \times 50, 16 \times 50, 20 \times 50, 24 \times 50,$ $28 \times 50, 32 \times 50, 36 \times 50, 40 \times 50, 44 \times 50, 48 \times 50$

4 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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